

ENHANCED COMPRESSIVE FATIGUE MODEL FOR IMPACT DAMAGED LAMINATES

Andrew T Rhead*, Richard Butler* & Giles W Hunt*

*Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Bath, UK

Keywords: *Delamination, post-buckling, strain energy release rate, fatigue*

Abstract

An enhanced analytical model for prediction of compressive fatigue threshold strains in composite plates with barely visible impact damage (BVID) is presented. The model represents the complex damage morphology as a single circular delamination at a critical level and calculates the strain at which thin-film buckling of the circular delaminated region occurs. The threshold strain is defined as the strain at which the strain energy release rate for the post-buckled delaminated plies is equal to the critical Mode I value (G_{IC}) for the resin. The model predicts the critical through-thickness level for delamination and also the sensitivity to experimental error in geometric measurements of the damage area. Results obtained using the model show an agreement of fatigue strain to within 4% of experimental values for four sets of data reported in the literature.

1 Introduction

In comparison to other currently used aerospace materials, laminated composites have excellent in-plane properties but are prone to delamination damage from out-of-plane impact loads. Such damage, which is often difficult to detect and is known as Barely Visible Impact Damage (BVID), can significantly reduce the compressive strength. Further reductions can occur when fatigue loading causes the damage to propagate from the initial site. This increasing area of damage can lead to widespread delamination and subsequent failure of the component.

At present the propagation of BVID is suppressed in design by applying empirically derived strain limits at ultimate levels of load. Typically these so-called damage tolerant strain limits take a value of around 4500 μ strain. Curtis et

al [1] have shown that there is a wide variation in threshold strain; indeed for one particular laminate of T800/924 material, damage did not propagate after 10^6 cycles at a fatigue strain of 3100 μ strain and for a IM7/977 laminate, a fatigue strain of 5000 μ strain was acceptable.

Clearly there is a need to explore the wide deviation in threshold strain and an excellent opportunity to save weight by increasing the damage tolerance limit, but this requires accurate prediction of the behaviour of delaminated composite materials under compressive strain. Such strain can promote buckling of sublaminates in the damaged region which causes opening of the delamination. With these points in mind, it is obvious that a mechanical model is required that accurately predicts the threshold strain for a general laminate.

The static propagation problem was addressed by Chai et al in [2]. They produced a simple 1D propagation model based on beam theory with the simplifying assumption that all the layers in the laminate were homogenous and isotropic. A 2D initial buckling model for multiple delaminations has been derived using a Rayleigh-Ritz formulation by Suemasu et al [3] and a similar 1D Rayleigh-Ritz model by Hunt et al [4] drew attention to the concept of a critical depth of delamination in the context of post-buckling response. More recently, Butler et al [5] presented a new method for compressive fatigue which included anisotropy and was based on a combination of 2D finite strip buckling and 1D beam propagation, where the complexity of the morphology and propagation of damage was represented by the energy requirements for final stage static growth of a single delamination at a critical depth within the sample.

The aim of the current paper is to present an enhanced version of the earlier model (hereafter the beam model) [5] for predicting the magnitude of fatigue strain required to propagate an area of BVID at a critical delamination level. The new

enhanced model (hereafter the plate model) uses an updated propagation approach based on plate bending energy together with damage principles similar to those proposed by Hwang and Liu [6]. In their work with 2D plane strain FE models, they suggest that buckling of a composite plate with multiple delaminations arising from out of plane impact damage can be simplified to buckling of a plate with a single delamination at a critical level in the laminate. Melin and Schön [7] report this critical level to be at a depth of around 10%-20% of the total thickness. The plate model is applied to the example problems reported in the experimental studies of [1], [7], [8] and [9]. Finally, it is used to indicate an optimised laminate stacking sequence that resists this propagation by maximising the threshold strain.

2 Analytical Model

The plate model is based on the conditions apparent in the final stages of fatigue damage growth. In particular, delaminations at a significant depth within the sample are assumed to have buckled and subsequently opened. An assumption is made that the BVID, viewed using non-destructive testing (NDT) (see Fig. 4 and [7]), can be accurately modelled as a single delamination at a critical level. The delamination, circular in shape with diameter l , is an approximation of the central region of initial BVID. The plate model requires the calculation of the buckling strain ε^C of the delaminated circular region. The process of calculating ε^C is described below and is reliant on the composite buckling program VICONOPT written by Williams et al [10]. The delaminated plate is modelled as a thin film such that the plate boundary along the circular perimeter of the delamination is assumed to be clamped. To obtain ε^C , VICONOPT uses the loadings placed on the thin film by axial compression of the full laminate. The loads acting on the delaminated plate $\{N\}_D$ are determined by obtaining the strain $\{\varepsilon\}_L$ of the full laminate when unit axial strain is applied. $\{N\}_D$ is then calculated, by assuming compatibility of strain from,

$$\{N\}_D = [A]_D \{\varepsilon\}_L \quad (1)$$

where $[A]_D$ is the in-plane membrane stiffness matrix of the delaminated plate. Note that although uni-axial load is applied to the full laminate, Eq. 1 may result in bi-axial load and shear being applied to the delaminated plate.

Fig. 1. Thin film model showing (a) plan view of circular delaminated plate with nodes and strips to illustrate VICONOPT discretisation, (b) central section through AB (pre-buckling), (c) (post-buckled) central section.

The delaminated plate can be unbalanced and asymmetric, which will give rise to fully populated matrices for in-plane membrane stiffness $[A]_D$, out-of-plane bending stiffness $[D]_D$, and coupling stiffness $[B]_D$. However, VICONOPT buckling analysis is fully general, and can analyse such laminates. The program models the problem as a series of finite strips. For the results presented later, 6 equal width strips were used with 12 constrained nodes at the junction of these strips and the circular boundary, see Fig. 1(a).

It is now possible to derive the energy released as the length of the delamination increases from l to $l + \delta l$, where δl is an infinitesimal length. The first step is to calculate the Mode I strain energy release rate G_I for propagation of the delamination. The non-linear response in the post-buckled central strip AB of Fig. 1 is represented by Fig. 2, where A_{11} is the pre-buckling stiffness of the strip and

rA_{11} is the axial stiffness following buckling. The strain energy due to bending integrated over the complete area of the delamination is derived from the area a_1 of Fig. 2, i.e.

$$U_1 = \int_0^l A_{11} \varepsilon^C (\varepsilon - \varepsilon^C) dx$$

$$U_1 = A_{11} l \varepsilon^C (\varepsilon - \varepsilon^C) \quad (2)$$

This result comes from the fact that in the linear context of critical buckling, the bending energy stored exactly equals the in-plane or stretching energy released [11] (p.171). The remaining axial strain energy is derived from the areas a_2 and a_3 ,

$$U_2 = \int_0^l \frac{A_{11}}{2} [(\varepsilon^C)^2 + r(\varepsilon - \varepsilon^C)^2] dx$$

$$U_2 = \frac{A_{11}}{2} l [(\varepsilon^C)^2 + r(\varepsilon - \varepsilon^C)^2] \quad (3)$$

The bending strain energy release rate (SERR) for propagation in the x -direction is then given by,

$$\frac{\partial U_1}{\partial l} = A_{11} \varepsilon^C (\varepsilon - \varepsilon^C) \quad (4)$$

and the corresponding axial SERR (the strain energy released by the adjacent undelaminated plate) is,

$$\frac{A_{11}}{2} \varepsilon^2 - \frac{\partial U_2}{\partial l} = \frac{A_{11}}{2} (\varepsilon - \varepsilon^C) [\varepsilon(1-r) + \varepsilon^C(1+r)] \quad (5)$$

where,

$$\frac{A_{11}}{2} \varepsilon^2 = \frac{d}{dl} \int \frac{A_{11}}{2} \varepsilon^2 dl \quad (6)$$

represents the axial strain energy stored in the unbuckled, undelaminated strip (per unit length). Hence the difference between Eq. 6 and the axial strain stored in the buckled delaminated region per unit length is the axial strain energy available for release (Eq. 5). Therefore the Mode I SERR when the delamination grows in the x direction is given by,

$$G_1 = \frac{\partial U_1}{\partial l} + \frac{A_{11}}{2} \varepsilon^2 - \frac{\partial U_2}{\partial l} \quad (7)$$

which implies,

$$G_1 = \frac{A_{11}}{2} (\varepsilon - \varepsilon^C) [\varepsilon(1-r) + \varepsilon^C(3+r)] \quad (8)$$

Note that the axial SERR of Eq. 5 is identical to the equivalent expression in [5]. However, the bending SERR of Eq. 4 replaces the following expression used previously in [5],

$$\frac{\partial U_1}{\partial l} = \frac{4\pi^2 D_{11}}{l^2} (\varepsilon - \varepsilon^C) \quad (9)$$

In both cases the presence of the term $(\varepsilon - \varepsilon^C)$ ensures no bending energy is released until buckling has occurred and the delamination has opened.

Fig. 2. Strain energy in a post-buckled strip at axial strain ε . N_x is axial load per unit width and the sum of a_2 and a_3 , integrated over the strip length l , is equal to U_2 of Eq. 3. Area a_1 is represented by U_1 of Eq. 2, where the latter is the bending energy of the delaminated plate.

An essential difference between the two models is the boundary conditions placed on them, as illustrated in Fig. 3. The 1D bending case, Fig. 3(b) and Eq. 9, is described by a single fourth order ordinary differential equation in one direction which allows only four conditions to be placed on the transverse boundaries, in this case clamped conditions at $x = 0$ and $x = l$. This leaves the longitudinal boundaries unrestrained which is an unrealistic representation of what happens to the plate under compression, particularly when fibres

within the laminate are aligned in $\pm 45^\circ$ or 90° directions. Equation 4 gives a better representation of the bending energy released because it takes into account the effects of transverse bending and twisting moments. A consequence of this derivation is that the effect of the circular boundary is taken into account.

Note that unlike Chai et al [2], the plate model does not include any terms that refer implicitly or explicitly to Poisson’s ratio effects. This is due to assumed continuity along the transverse (radial) edge of the delamination. Hence it is assumed that strain energy is only released in the longitudinal (normal) direction. However, forces do occur in the transverse direction due to differences in Poisson’s ratio between the delaminated region and the full laminate, these forces may be compressive or tensile depending on whether the Poisson’s ratio of the delaminated region is larger or smaller than that of the full laminate.

Fig. 3. (a) Plate buckling mode with clamped circular boundaries and critical load N_x^C . (b) Beam buckling mode with clamped transverse boundaries and critical load $N_x^C = 4\pi^2 D_{11} / l^2$.

A final issue to resolve in this section is the value for the ratio of post-buckling stiffness to pre-buckling stiffness r . Results obtained in [12] and [13] suggest that $r = 0.5$ for post-buckled plates with clamped boundaries. Here the constraint conditions are different and a value of $r = 0$ is chosen in the following examples for simplicity,

although comparison with $r = 0.5$ is also considered.

3 Experimental Examples

The plate model was tested for validation purposes on a range of laminates with varying materials and lay-ups taken from the literature ([1], [7], [8], and [9]). These papers used differing test data and a brief summary of each is given below. The material properties are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Material properties of the laminates, t is layer thickness.

Material	E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	ν_{12}	t (mm)	G_{IC} (J/m ²)
AS4/8552	128.0	10.3	6.0	0.3	0.25	261
XAS/914	135.0	8.5	6.0	0.3	0.125	103
HTA/6376	133.0	10.8	3.6	0.29	0.13	240

3.1 AS4/8552 coupons [9]

BVID was introduced centrally into coupons of 4mm thick AS4/8552 material with lay-up $[(45,0,-45,90)]_{2S}$ using 6kN of static load (equivalent to 10J of impact energy) applied to one side of the specimens while they were clamped over a rectangular window. The central delaminations created were approximately 27mm in diameter as indicated by acoustography images from [9]. Samples prepared with BVID were placed in axial compression fatigue ($R=10$) and prevented from buckling by an anti-buckling guide which left an exposed central circular region 85mm in diameter. Note that a fatigue limit of 3600 μ strain was incorrectly reported for these coupons in [5] since that study did not obtain upper and lower bounds on the threshold strain, and hence was conservative. A more extensive set of results, which did bound the threshold strain, was given in [9].

3.2 XAS/914 coupons [1]

BVID was introduced into coupons of 2mm thick XAS/914 material with lay-up $[(45,-45,0,90)]_{2S}$ using an incident energy level of 7J. Impacts were repeated at 55mm spacing across large panels clamped in circular steel frames 100mm in diameter. The impacted panels were cut into 250mm long and 50mm wide coupons and tested with an anti-buckling guide in place to prevent overall buckling. Images from [1] suggest

the BVID damage for these samples fits within a 15mm diameter circle.

Fig. 4. C-scans and contour maps from [7] following propagation of damage in quasi isotropic (top) and 0° dominated (bottom) laminates. The left hand plots are views of the front (impact) face and the right hand plots are of the back face. Negative contours denote deflection towards the back face.

3.3 HTA/6376 coupons [7] and [8]

BVID was introduced into coupons of 6.24mm thick HTA/6376 material with a so-called zero dominated (ZD) lay-up $[45,-45,0,90,45,-45,0_2,(45,-45,0,90)_2,45,-45,0_2,45,-45,0,90]_s$ and a quasi-isotropic (QI) lay-up $[(90,-45,45,0)_s,(0,45,-45,90)_s]_3$ using an impact energy of 27J. Note because of the asymmetry of the HTA/6376 QI laminate it is necessary to establish impact and back faces in order to give the correct lay-up for the sublaminates involved in propagation. The impact face is assumed to be the top of the laminate, defined by stacking sequence, which implies the delaminated plate is composed of the bottom layers of the laminate. This assumption was confirmed by comparing model results to reported values using both faces of the laminate as the impact face in the analytical model. Figure 4 shows C-scan images from [7] depicting the BVID damage, which was assumed to approximate a circular area of diameter 50mm. Coupons were 156mm wide and 450mm long, with gripping zones 156mm wide and 100mm long at either end of the specimen. An anti-buckling

window was applied leaving a 100mm x 100mm square able to buckle under compressive loading.

4 Comparison of experimental results with analytical model

To obtain the critical level of delamination it is necessary to solve Eq. 8 for ε , hence,

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\varepsilon^C}{(1-r)} \left(-(1+r) + \sqrt{(1+r)^2 + (1-r) \left((3+r) + \frac{2G_1}{(\varepsilon^C)^2 A_{11}} \right)} \right) \quad (10)$$

Now using $G_1 = G_{1C}$, the critical Mode I SERR for the material provided by the manufacturer, see Table 1, it is possible to determine the threshold strain $\varepsilon = \varepsilon_{th}$ for each layer. Clearly the level with lowest ε_{th} will begin to release energy first and hence will be the first to propagate. Alternatively, G_1 can be plotted against strain for each level and the threshold strain can be determined from the intercept of these curves with the G_{1C} value, the first to intercept being the strain and level at which propagation occurs, e.g. see Fig. 5. Hence the plate model indicates the strain required for propagation to occur.

Fig. 5. Strain energy release rate (SERR) for propagation at 4, 5 and 6 ply depths in HTA/6376 ZD laminate.

It also predicts the level within the laminate at which damage first grows beyond the circular perimeter of initial damage. Melin and Schön [7] suggest that propagation occurs at a depth of around

10-20% of total thickness for their plates so all levels were analysed from approximately 10% up to 25% of total thickness. Figure 5 shows that damage first grows at a depth of 5 plies in the HTA/6376 ZD laminate. The analytical model predicts the same critical depth for the HTA/6376 QI laminate. The experimental and analytical results for threshold strain are presented for comparison in Table 2. The experimental results are a summary of those reported in [1], [7] and [9], with experimental data set out in the previous section. Table 3 specifies the buckling strain ϵ^C , determined by VICONOPT according to the procedure set out in Section 2, for the delaminated plate corresponding to the level at which propagation first occurs. The plate model predicts that the BVID propagates first at a depth of 2 plies in the AS4/8552 laminate and at a depth of 3 plies in the XAS/914 laminate.

Table 2. Experimental and analytical threshold strains for various laminates described in Section 3.

Material	Threshold strain (μstrain):	
	Experimental	Analytical
AS4/8552	3100	3026
XAS/914	3400	3397
HTA/6376 QI	3300	3408
HTA/6376 ZD	3300	3253

Table 3. VICONOPT buckling strains for thin sublaminates at which the delamination first propagates. Note that the sublaminate stacking sequences retain the orientation of the full laminate, i.e. the top layer of the sublaminate is the one closest to the impact face.

Material	Sublaminate Lay-up	Buckling Strain (μstrain)
AS4/8552	0,45	1097
XAS/914	0,-45,45	2763
HTA/6376 QI	90,90,-45,45,0	1108
HTA/6376 ZD	45,90,0,-45,45	1440

5 Discussion

Although the model is tested on relatively few laminates it should be noted that their properties are extremely varied in terms of input energy, material, lay-up and thickness as can be seen in Section 3. This suggests that unlike the beam model, which was limited to thinner laminates with less complex lay-ups, the plate model is able to predict threshold strain values for a wide range of problems.

Figure 6 highlights the precision of the plate model. The difference between the analytical strain predicted by the plate model and the experimental result is at most 4%. Unfortunately, the ability of

the model to predict at which level crack propagation first occurs remains almost entirely untested. Only Butler et al [5] reported at which level the delamination grew. However in this case the model prediction of 2nd ply crack growth matches their observation that growth was at the 2nd and 3rd lamina level. It is worth noting that, as expected, when an axial post-buckled stiffness of $r = 0.5$ is used in Eq. 10, the threshold strain values all increase. The greatest increase occurred for the HTA/6376 QI laminate, where an 8% difference in experimental and analytical results was calculated. Propagation, in this case, was predicted at the sixth ply level.

Fig. 6. Comparison of threshold strains.

As explained in Section 2 the critical (buckling) strains in Table 3 were calculated in VICONOPT using 12 constrained nodes and six strips (Fig. 1). However, it is possible to model the boundary of the delamination in a number of different ways, described below.

The first consideration is to alter the constraints placed on the boundary of the delamination by the nodes. In the results reported in Section 4 full restraint was applied at each node in VICONOPT which is the equivalent to a fully clamped boundary. However in the methods reported in Section 3 buckling guides were used around the delaminations. These guides constrain rotation, bending and out of plane movement; not in-plane compression/Poisson effects, although these may be partially constrained by the undelaminated region. Hence it was necessary to understand the effect of altering the nodal boundary conditions in VICONOPT.

Secondly it is possible to increase the number of nodes and therefore strips that describe the circular delamination and its boundary. In VICONOPT nodes are used to describe the edge of the delamination, which means the problem is discretely constrained at intervals around this boundary. Increasing the number of nodes has the

Fig. 7. Effect of varying buckling strain on threshold strain for HTA/6376 QI laminate.

Fig. 8. Effect of varying buckling strain on threshold strain for HTA/6376 ZD laminate.

effect of bringing the boundary closer to the test situation of a continuously constrained buckling guide.

A further consideration is the spacing of the nodes around the circular delamination. The results presented in Section 4 use a fixed strip width which leads to an uneven distribution of nodes around the circumference of the delamination and hence some regions are more tightly constrained than others. An alternative approach is to fix the arc length between nodes and to alter the strip width, thus producing equally spaced constraints around the delamination boundary.

The final aspect tested was the diameter of the delamination, this was considered necessary as the diameter is obtained from NDT and is only approximate.

Table 4. Effects of alterations to VICONOPT problem data on buckling strain and threshold strain for AS4/8552.

Alteration	ϵ^c (μstrain)	ϵ_{th} (μstrain)
None	1097	3026
Rotation, bending and out of plane movement restrained only	1076	3025
18 Nodes	1141	3030
Equal arc length	1087	3026
Delamination diameter +5%	995	3023

All these considerations were thoroughly tested and an example of the effects on the buckling and threshold strains can be seen in Table 4. For the case of the AS4/8552 laminate note that, although the buckling strain changed considerably with these alterations, the threshold strain varied very little. It is possible to determine just how sensitive the threshold strain for a particular laminate is to variations in critical buckling strain. This can be illustrated using graphical methods, see Figs. 7, 8 and 9. These figures show the variation in threshold strain brought about by a $\pm 10\%$ variation in ϵ^c . Clearly for the HTA/6376 QI results shown in Fig. 7 the variation has little effect. For the HTA/6376 ZD the variation in threshold strain is a little more pronounced but still relatively small. Note here that the variations being considered in ϵ^c are not due to changes in material properties as this would result in a different curve in Figs. 7, 8 and 9. Comparing Figs. 7 and 8 using gradient considerations it can be seen that the sensitivity of the laminate to buckling strain is determined by the proximity of the VICONOPT critical strain to the minimum of Eq. 10 given by,

Fig. 9. Effect of varying buckling strain on threshold strain for XAS/914 laminate.

$$\frac{\partial \varepsilon_{th}}{\partial \varepsilon^C} = 0 \quad (11)$$

Which, for $r = 0$ implies;

$$\varepsilon^C = \sqrt{\frac{G_{1C}}{6A_{11}}} \quad (12)$$

This sensitivity can be quantified by creating a sensitivity ratio, R_S ,

$$\frac{f(\varepsilon^C(1+\alpha)) - f(\varepsilon^C(1-\alpha))}{2\alpha\varepsilon^C} = R_S \quad (13)$$

where f defines the RHS of Eq. 10 and α defines the variation of buckling strain, (i.e. $\alpha = 0.1$ would represent a 10% variation of buckling strain). The denominator is the spread of the buckling strains and the numerator is the projection of these strains onto the threshold strain axis. A sensitivity ratio close to zero indicates a high tolerance to variation of buckling strain. R_S can be used as a comparative tool for laminates and will indicate the laminate with the lowest sensitivity to buckling strain which may in turn show which laminate is least sensitive to damage size.

Equation 12 shows it is possible to attain a low

value of R_S by choosing laminates with a certain ratio of G_{1C} to A_{11} . In particular a high ratio, which pushes the minimum to the right, is achieved by a large G_{1C} and a low A_{11} , although care must be taken in altering A_{11} as this will affect ε^C . An excellent illustrative example of these effects is shown in Fig. 9. The material XAS/914, has a brittle resin and hence a low G_{1C} (see Table 1) which combines with stiff fibres (giving a high A_{11}) to push the minimum to the left while giving a large ε^C which results in an R_S of almost 1. Hence for this data, a 10% change in ε^C produces a change of almost 10% in ε_{th} .

5.1 Fatigue resistant laminate

As a design application for the plate model a fatigue resistant, manually optimised laminate is now considered. The principle for the optimization was based on two factors; increasing the delaminated plate buckling strain and reducing the SERR. The former was achieved by putting all the $\pm 45^\circ$ layers to the outer faces of the laminate, thus increasing buckling resistance. The latter was achieved by moving all the 0° fibres to the central region as these fibres tend to cause strain energy to release earlier in effect increasing the gradient of

the curves of Figs. 5 and 10. With these considerations in mind a manually optimised stacking sequence of $[(45,-45)_6, 0_2, (90,0_2)_2, (90,0)_2]_s$ was chosen. The optimised laminate was assumed to have been made from the HTA/6376 material and had the same area of damage and the same number of 0° , $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° layers as the HTA/6376 ZD laminate described above. The results obtained from VICONOPT indicate a buckling strain of $1941 \mu\text{strain}$ and the analytical results predict a threshold strain of $3800 \mu\text{strain}$. Hence the plate model predicts a threshold strain value for this laminate which is approximately 17% higher than the threshold obtained for the HTA/6376 ZD laminate above. The model also predicted propagation occurring between the 5th and 6th layers which gives a delaminated region with stacking sequence $[45,-45,45,-45,45]$. Note however, that the threshold strain value and delamination depth have yet to be experimentally confirmed.

Fig. 10. Strain energy release rate for propagation at 4, 5 and 6 ply depths in optimised HTA/6376 laminate.

6 Conclusions and future work

The new analytical model is based on the assumption that the propagation of BVID can be simplified to propagation at a single level within the laminate and is dependent on only three parameters of the problem G_{IC} , ε^C and A_{11} . The plate model predicts threshold strain with at most a 4% error compared to experimental values for the laminates tested and is within 1% for some cases. Applying the model to a laminate with damage tolerant $45^\circ/-$

45° layers protecting the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ (such as the laminate in Section 5.1) shows that these types of lay-up offer enhanced damage tolerance. It should be noted that the laminate was manually optimised to maximise buckling strain and minimise SERR. It was not optimised using any specific design strategy nor did it consider other constraints, such as buckling or aeroelasticity. Nevertheless, the model could provide an excellent tool for designing laminates in the future and could remove the need for expensive and time consuming fatigue testing. Finally it remains to experimentally verify the threshold strain value determined for the manually optimised HTA/6376 laminate.

Further future work will include the development of an analytical model for damage size prediction, which will make the process entirely analytic. Other boundary and initial conditions, in particular those arising from a free edge or oblique impact damage event will be considered. An extension of the fatigue strength model to a static strength model will also be derived.

Acknowledgements

Andrew Rhead is sponsored by a partnership of the Great Western Research (GWR) alliance and Airbus UK. The paper is a part of a larger body of work being carried out by a consortium involving GWR, Airbus UK, Augusta Westland, Rolls Royce, the University of Bath, the University of Bristol and the University of Exeter. The authors would like to thank all of the above parties for their continuing support.

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